

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MOTHER–CHILD RELATIONSHIPS IN COMPLETE AND INCOMPLETE FAMILIES

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Abstract. *This article examines the socio-psychological characteristics of mother–child relationships in complete and incomplete families, with particular attention to adolescents’ perceptions of maternal behavior and mothers’ parenting attitudes. The study involved 221 respondents, including participants from complete and incomplete family contexts. Diagnostic data were processed using IBM SPSS 20, and normal distribution was tested through the Kolmogorov–Smirnov criterion. Since the data met normality requirements, Student’s *t*-test was applied to compare group differences. The findings revealed that adolescents from incomplete families perceived lower maternal positive interest and higher directiveness and hostility than those from complete families. Mothers in complete families demonstrated stronger child acceptance, cooperation, and emotional attachment. Gender-based analysis within incomplete families showed greater maternal control toward sons and stronger symbiotic attachment toward daughters. The study concludes that family structure and gender-related dynamics significantly influence mother–child interaction, emotional support, and adolescents’ socio-psychological development. These findings provide practical implications for family counselling.*

Keywords: *acceptance–rejection of the child, cooperation, symbiosis, control, attitude toward the child’s failures, positive interest, directiveness, hostility, autonomy, instability, competition, collaboration, compromise, physical aggression, indirect aggression, irritability, negativism, resentment, suspiciousness, verbal aggression, sense of guilt.*

Introduction. The main issue advanced in our research is the study of the socio-psychological characteristics of mother–child relationships in incomplete families. Based on this objective, the factors influencing mother–child relationships in incomplete families are examined.

It should be emphasized that the results obtained from the diagnostic procedures aimed at studying the socio-psychological characteristics of mother–child relationships in incomplete families were entered into the IBM SPSS 20 software package, and initially the conformity of the variation series to the law of normal distribution was tested using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov criterion. According to the results of this criterion, it was determined that the participants’ indicators corresponded to the normal distribution criterion. Therefore, Student’s *t*-test was employed to compare the research results.

Main part. It is known that, for the purpose of scientifically investigating children’s perceptions of maternal behavior, E. S. Schaefer’s methodology entitled “Children’s Description of Parental Behavior” was selected [4,5,6]. This methodology makes it possible to determine how maternal behavior is perceived by the child and encompasses such relationship dimensions as positive interest, directiveness, hostility, autonomy, and inconsistency. The questionnaire was

administered to the selected group of respondents, and the obtained results were analyzed both quantitatively and qualitatively and are presented in Table 1.

1-table. Differences in Children's Perceptions of Maternal Behavior Across Family Types (N = 221)

(According to Student's t-test)

Components	Family types	N	Average value	t (Student's t-test value)	p (confidence level)
Positive Interest	Complete Family	120	12,68	2,195	p≤0,05
	Incomplete Family	101	8,42		
Directiveness	Complete Family	120	9,94	-4,618	p≤0,01
	Incomplete Family	101	13,56		
Hostility	Complete Family	120	9,29	-2,124	p≤0,05
	Incomplete Family	101	12,50		
Autonomy	Complete Family	120	8,37	1,496	p>0,05
	Incomplete Family	101	6,96		
Instability	Complete Family	120	9,92	0,961	p>0,05
	Incomplete Family	101	8,93		

According to the results presented in Table 1, when the psychological characteristics of children's perceptions of maternal behavior were examined across family types, statistically significant differences were identified in the positive interest component ($t = 2.195$; $p \leq 0.05$). This indicates that adolescents raised in complete families, compared to those raised in incomplete families, tend to evaluate their mothers' attitudes toward them as being at a normative level; that is, mothers are more often perceived as consistently attentive, caring, open in their interactions while taking their children's wishes into account, and positively accepting their opinions and views. This suggests that adolescents raised in incomplete families are more likely to perceive their mothers' attitudes toward them as limited, particularly characterized by emotional coldness, a low level of emotional support, and a tendency to avoid communication.

When the respondents' indicators regarding the manifestation of directiveness were compared, statistically significant differences were identified between the groups ($t = -4.618$; $p \leq 0.01$). This can be explained by the fact that attempts by mothers to induce feelings of guilt in their children, maintain constant control over them, negatively perceive their children's personal opinions, consider themselves always right, and resolve interpersonal problems through punishment are observed more frequently among adolescents raised in incomplete families than among those raised in complete families. Thus, in incomplete families, mother-child relationships are more often characterized by control-based interactions, emotional pressure, and restrictions on personal freedom, which may negatively affect psychological processes such as independent thinking, initiative, and social adaptation.

When the respondents' indicators regarding the manifestation of hostility were examined, statistically significant differences were identified ($t = -2.124$; $p \leq 0.05$). These findings indicate that behaviors such as mothers displaying aggressive attitudes toward their children, excessive strictness, attempts to dominate or "defeat" the child as a rival, suspicious attitudes toward the child accompanied by emotional coldness, and critical or harsh interactions with the child are observed more frequently among adolescents raised in incomplete families than among those raised in complete families. The results suggest that, in incomplete families, the increasing family burden placed on mothers—where they assume not only child-rearing responsibilities but also financial and social obligations alone—contributes to greater emotional exhaustion, irritability, and tendencies toward harshness.

It should be noted that, during the course of the study, no statistically significant differences were observed in the autonomy and instability components when examining differences in children's perceptions of maternal behavior across family types. This suggests that such characteristics of family relationships as suppressing the child's wishes, indifference or inattentiveness to the child's problems, as well as inconsistent attitudes toward the child—simultaneously displaying strength and caution, distrust and suspicion—do not differ fundamentally between complete and incomplete families.

While the above section provided a general analysis of the differences in children's perceptions of maternal behavior across family types, the following section separately examines differences in mothers' attitudes toward their children within the context of family type. The indicators obtained from mothers raising children in complete and incomplete families, based on A. Ya. Varga and V. V. Stolin's methodology entitled "Parents' attitude towards children" are presented in Table 2 [1,2,3].

2-table. Differences in Mothers' Attitudes Toward Their Children Across Family Types (N = 221)

(According to Student's t-test)

Components	Family types	N	Average value	t (Student's t-test value)	p (confidence level)
Acceptance of the Child	Complete Family	120	10,35	2,251	$p \leq 0,05$
	Incomplete Family	101	7,56		
Cooperation	Complete Family	120	9,57	2,601	$p \leq 0,01$
	Incomplete Family	101	5,87		
Symbiosis	Complete Family	120	8,80	2,806	$p \leq 0,01$
	Incomplete Family	101	5,77		
Control	Complete Family	120	4,11	0,145	$p > 0,05$
	Incomplete Family	101	4,06		
	Complete Family	120	3,25	-0,664	$p > 0,05$

Attitude Toward the Child's Failures	Incomplete Family	101	3,54		
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According to the results presented in Table 2, statistically significant differences were identified in the child acceptance component among mothers raising children in complete and incomplete families ($t = 2.251; p \leq 0.05$). These indicators suggest that emotional support in interactions with the child, expressions of affection and care, trust based on friendly relationships, acceptance of the child as they are, positive attitudes toward independent thinking, and efforts to understand and consider the child's needs were observed more frequently in complete families than in incomplete families. Therefore, the lower manifestation of this component in incomplete families may be explained by the fact that mothers are often under economic and social pressures, leading to stress and consequently weakening the emotional bond between mother and child.

When the respondents' indicators regarding the manifestation of cooperation were examined, statistically significant differences were identified ($t = -2.601; p \leq 0.01$). This can be explained by the fact that mothers in complete families, compared to mothers in incomplete families, more frequently demonstrate trust and encourage independence in responsible tasks, listen to and consider their children's opinions, apply guidance-oriented rather than punishment-based management, and respect their children as individuals. These findings indicate that mothers raising children in incomplete families are more inclined toward authoritarian and control-based parenting styles, that is, a directive approach.

When the respondents' research results regarding the symbiosis component were compared, statistically significant differences were identified in this factor ($t = -2.806; p \leq 0.01$). The findings indicate that mothers raising children in complete families, compared to those in incomplete families, demonstrate a deeper level of emotional attachment in their relationships with their children, greater care and concern for them, stronger efforts to maintain supportive and positive interactions, and a greater tendency to provide their children with a sense of dignity, security, and protection.

It should be emphasized that, during the course of the study, no statistically significant differences were identified between mothers raising children in complete and incomplete families with regard to the manifestation of control and attitudes toward children's failures. This indicates that the management of children's behavior, the authoritarian or democratic nature of parenting styles, respect for children's opinions and emotions, as well as attitudes toward children's abilities, shortcomings, successes, and failures do not differ fundamentally across family types.

In addition, based on these methodologies, children's perceptions of maternal behavior in incomplete families were examined separately according to gender, and the results are presented in Table 3.

3-table. Differences in Children's Perceptions of Maternal Behavior in Incomplete Families Across Gender Categories (N = 101)
(According to Student's t-test)

Components	Gender types	N	Average value	t (Student's t-test value)	p (confidence level)
Acceptance of the Child	Boys	52	9,44	1,195	p>0,05
	Girls	49	9,42		

Cooperation	Boys	52	8,94	-1,618	p>0,05
	Girls	49	8,96		
Symbiosis	Boys	52	9,29	-1,122	p>0,05
	Girls	49	9,31		
Control	Boys	52	12,37	2,493	p≤0,05
	Girls	49	6,96		
Attitude Toward the Child's Failures	Boys	52	7,17	0,988	p>0,05
	Girls	49	7,05		

According to the results presented in Table 3, when the respondents' results for the positive interest component were compared, no statistically significant differences were identified in this factor ($t = 1.195$; $p > 0.05$). These findings indicate that adolescent girls and boys raised in incomplete families do not differ substantially in their perceptions of their mothers' critical attitudes, positive interest, consistent attention, care, and willingness to fulfill their children's wishes and needs. The research results further demonstrated that children's descriptions of maternal behavior among both boys and girls are not determined by gender.

When the respondents' results regarding the manifestation of the directiveness component were examined, no statistically significant differences were identified between the indicators ($t = -1.618$; $p > 0.05$). This suggests that, in incomplete families, children's identification of maternal behaviors—such as mothers perceiving themselves as sacrificing their lives for their children, asserting their authority to prevent children from making mistakes, and resolving problems through punishment—is similarly observed across gender categories.

When the respondents' results regarding the hostility component were analyzed, no statistically significant differences were identified among these indicators ($t = -1.122$; $p > 0.05$). This suggests that, in incomplete families, boys and girls raised by their mothers do not differ significantly in perceiving maternal behavior as characterized by suspicious attitudes that create emotional distance, manifestations of physical and verbal aggression, excessively critical interactions, and tendencies to withdraw from their children.

When the respondents' indicators regarding the manifestation of autonomy were compared, statistically significant differences were identified between the groups ($t = 2.493$; $p \leq 0.05$). The findings indicate that adolescent boys and girls raised in incomplete families differ in their descriptions of maternal behavior, with boys more frequently perceiving their mothers as failing to accept them as individuals, subordinating their wishes to maternal goals, and displaying indifference toward their problems compared to girls.

No statistically significant differences were identified between the respondents' results regarding the instability component ($t = 0.988$; $p > 0.05$). The research findings indicate that there are no substantial differences between boys and girls raised by single mothers in incomplete families with respect to this indicator. This suggests that the level of instability in relationships among children growing up in incomplete families does not differ significantly according to gender characteristics.

Furthermore, based on these methodologies, differences in mothers' attitudes toward their children in incomplete families were examined across gender categories, and the results are presented in Table 4.

According to the results presented in Table 4, when the respondents' results regarding the symbiosis component were compared, statistically significant differences were identified in this

factor ($t = -2.724$; $p \leq 0.01$). The findings indicate that mothers in incomplete families are more likely to seek emotional and social closeness, companionship, friendship, and emotional support from their daughters than from their sons. This situation demonstrates the existence of significant differences in mothers' attitudes toward daughters compared to sons.

4-table. Differences in Mothers' Attitudes Toward Their Children in Incomplete Families Across Gender Categories (N = 101)
(According to Student's t-test)

Components	Gender types	N	Average value	t (Student's t-test value)	p (confidence level)
Acceptance of the Child	O'g'il bolalar	52	8,42	1,048	$p > 0,05$
	Qiz bolalar	49	7,78		
Cooperation	O'g'il bolalar	52	5,37	-0,552	$p > 0,05$
	Qiz bolalar	49	6,83		
Symbiosis	O'g'il bolalar	52	7,80	-2,724	$p \leq 0,01$
	Qiz bolalar	49	11,24		
Control	O'g'il bolalar	52	10,14	2,145	$p \leq 0,05$
	Qiz bolalar	49	6,08		
Attitude Toward the Child's Failures	O'g'il bolalar	52	7,48	-0,955	$p > 0,05$
	Qiz bolalar	49	7,59		

When the results concerning mothers' attitudes toward their children in relation to the control component were comparatively examined, statistically significant differences were identified between the groups ($t = 2.145$; $p \leq 0.05$). Based on these indicators, it should be emphasized that mothers raising children in incomplete families tend to exercise stronger control over their sons than over their daughters, more frequently applying boundaries, restrictions, punishment mechanisms, and authoritarian or democratic parenting approaches. Furthermore, these differences may serve as a methodological basis for developing recommendations regarding mother-child relationships within the framework of this study through a deeper examination of parenting styles in incomplete families.

The results revealed that, during the course of the study, no statistically significant differences were observed in mothers' attitudes toward their children in incomplete families with regard to child acceptance, cooperation, and attitudes toward children's failures. This suggests that mothers raising children in incomplete families demonstrate similar levels of emotional acceptance, emotional support in various situations, willingness to cooperate in performing certain tasks, and attitudes toward their children's achievements and shortcomings across gender categories.

Conclusion. Based on the above indicators, it can be emphasized that family type and gender-related dynamics within the family negatively influence interpersonal relationships between mothers and adolescent children in both complete and incomplete families. In particular, the absence of a father figure or insufficient emotional support in incomplete families adversely affects adolescents' socio-psychological development.

In conclusion, it can be stated that the instability of family structure, mothers' parenting approaches, the level of attention given to children, and the degree of emotional support directly influence the quality of interpersonal relationships. The way adolescent children feel in

communication with their mothers is directly associated with their self-esteem, social relationships, and future patterns of behavior.

While this section presented analyses of mothers' relationships with their children and children's perceptions of maternal behavior across family types and gender categories in complete and incomplete families, the following paragraph examines the characteristics of the interrelationship between mother-child relations in incomplete families.

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